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**NARRATIVES OF THREAT AND POWER IN
ELECTRONIC MEDIA: A CRITICAL DISCOURSE
ANALYSIS OF U.S.- CHINA COLD WAR
CHRONICLES**

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Narratives of Threat and Power in Electronic Media: A Critical Discourse Analysis of U.S.- China Cold War Chronicles

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Abstract

The escalating geopolitical rivalry between the United States and China has, in turn, created competing narratives of threat and power, discussed in the public eye largely through electronic media. This study examines how government officials in both the U.S. and

China discursively construct and circulate Cold War narratives through their language and communication in official statements. Using Fairclough's three-dimensional model of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), the study delves into the lexical items and discursive practices to understand ideological meanings behind the words. The data consists of electronic media press briefings and public addresses from the international and domestic election campaigns from March 2020 to April 2024. The data is analysed qualitatively using text and context-based analysis. The findings suggest that U.S. government officials draw on more negative's lexical items (like aggression, coercion and security threat) to construct China as a challenger to liberal order while Chinese government officials draw more on more favorable lexical items (like peaceful coexistence, mutual benefit and cooperation) to promote a counter-narrative of harmony and legitimacy. Both parties engage in strategic discursive practices of othering, legitimization and moral evaluation in order to perpetuate their ideological positioning. The study concludes that language is a significant instrument of geopolitical influence and shapes the ways in which understanding reproduces a space of dominance in the global communicative field.

Keywords: Threat, power, U.S.-China, cold-war

1. INTRODUCTION

The intensifying competition between the United States and China in the twenty-first century has emerged as a sort of "new Cold War," which has materialized into political language, media and strategic discourse (Lu, 2023). In a world configured around electronic media, the language of

political actors is utilized in both communicating ideas and wielding power and has ramifications on publics' perceptions in regard to international relations. According to Fairclough (1995), discourse is always ideological. Discourse can either help sustain or challenge the established pattern of power. Similarly, Van Dijk (2006) discusses that elites work to strengthen social relations and hierarchies through what discourse they decide to create. In the context of U.S.-China relations, choices of language and discursive strategies illustrate ways to create identity for both countries and situate the other in a conception of power and threat. The competition between these global powers is far more than economic or military confrontation; it also exists in the symbolic world of words and meanings. U.S. officials frame China as a geopolitical and ideological threat to democracy in liberal terms and routinely leverage negative terms which have lexical items like aggression, authoritarianism and unfair trade to describe China's global behavior (Hu & Li, 2025). On the other hand, Chinese officials frame themselves as cooperative and reciprocal by employing terms and concepts like peaceful development and win-win partnership (Lu, 2023). Such divergences in language illustrate a narrative construction from each side in which they justify their policies, appeal to their ideological mission and assert superiority over the other side. Electronic media serves to heighten these narratives, transforming select language choices into widespread narratives that shape global ideological public opinions.

While scholarship has addressed the framing of China in Western media (Mohammad & Abid, 2021; Xu & Xu, 2025) and investigated China's domestic media narratives, there is little comparative scholarship in the linguistic and ideological analysis of U.S. and Chinese official statements. Most of the existing literature discussing framing or an analysis of the international policy space does not combine a detailed linguistic analysis. The current research responds to this gap by implementing Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) to explore the most frequent lexical items and discursive strategies both sides utilize in objectifying the ongoing Cold War narratives. The study attempts to illuminate how lexical frequency and rhetorical framing facilitates the construction of threat and power, exposing the ideological framing captured in the government's use of language. The theoretical framing of this study is Fairclough's (1995) three-dimensional conceptualization of CDA as a framework to investigate relationships between textual, discursive and social practices. This framework enables

researchers to understand how language organizes agency on linguistic, institutional and socio-political contexts. Together with textual analysis and critical interpretation, the study locates political language as both a representation and practice of ideology. In doing so, the study contributes to a growing body of critical linguistic studies discussing language as a site of struggle, contestation, and domination. The findings aim to enrich understanding of how discourse acts as a mechanism of geopolitical domination and influence and that global rivalries are not only waged through policies and weapons but also through words that loan authority to challenge and curate international discourse.

1.1 Research Objectives

- To compare the most frequently made lexical choices by the U.S. and China officials to encourage or discourage the present and potential cold war situation.
- To identify the discursive strategies used by U.S. and China governments officials to construct the narratives of threat and power.

1.2 Research Questions

1. What lexical items have been used most frequently by the U.S. and China officials to encourage or discourage the present and potential cold war situation?
2. What discursive strategies have been used by U.S. and China governments officials to construct the narratives of threat and power?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. CDA in Political Discourse and Lexical Choice

Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) focuses on the various ways that language can represent ideologies; to represent power or dominance in a political text. Central to the formation of discourses of authority or preferably threat is the power of lexical selection. Mohammad and Abid (2021) have analyzed Trump's discourse on COVID-19, highlighting how he effectively evoked war metaphors and continually lexicalized expressions such as "enemy," or "Chinese virus" to construct China as an ideological threat to the world. Further, Lu (2023) describes how the discourses of U.S.-China competition draw on contrastive lexical fields like "democracy versus authoritarianism" to maintain a level of ideological distance while also indicating a competition in ideological supremacy. Hu and Li (2025) have outlined how the U.S. trade policy discourse has constructed China through new deictic markers (trade [unfair] + global [rules-based]) to legitimize the

containment of China as fabrication. These lexical strategies stemmed from a hierarchy of moral and economic superiority. Anwar, Butt, and Zuree (2024) provide insight on the combination of verbs chosen in Pakistani newspapers, transforming sometimes subtle lexicalization to relay a socio-ideological alignment in understanding political tone across national negotiation. Similarly, it is commonplace for CDA using Corpus-Based CDA to combine frequency analysis to measure ideological bias in terms of collocations grouped under heading like: "threat," "security," or, "stability." In short, collectively across U.S centered representations, we see that lexical choices have implications not only for representing political stance but also available intertextual maps to global power impact and influence. This offers a clear rationale for examining how U.S. and Chinese officials have leveraged language to heighten or deescalate tensions that resemble those of the Cold-War.

2.2 Discursive Strategies: Othering, Victimization and Legitimization

CDA determines some recurring, underlying discursive objectives including othering, victimization and legitimization to frame self-other binaries where the other is constructed in opposition to self. Afzaal et al. (2019) demonstrate that the Pakistani media frame China as a "trusted ally" and a "development partner" in ways that legitimize relations, showing positive identity frames that privilege China as a developmental partner and contrast this with an assumed stance of skepticism towards western nations. Ahmed et al. (2019) engage with social-media discourse specifically in the case of the CPEC project, suggesting that binaries of emotional framing label supporters as "patriots" and opponents as "traitors," resulting in overt discursive polarization. Similarly, Khan et al. (2021) point to the tendency of the Indian media to categorize China as a "strategic threat" or "expansionist" employing linguistic othering and a form of securitization to create images of the other. Anwar and Butt (2025) have analyzed the speech and rhetoric of Netanyahu's address at the UNGA, asserting that the combination of war metaphors and moral binaries such as a representation of "light versus darkness," serves to legitimize aggression by representing the self ultimately victimized by the other. Likewise, through an analysis of the rhetoric of Israeli officials, Anwar, Butt, and Shahzadi (2024) have explored the role of delegitimization in a civilizational context and transmit the notion of "we defend" versus "they attack," forming a logical structure whereby "we belong to a civilizational high ground." This sort of discursive

strategy can be observed in global political discourse to shape a narrative of defense even if consistently projecting the other as aggressive in intention or irreconcilable. In terms of the U.S.- China construct, a great deal is fabricated through the language of 'freedom' or 'rules-based order' intended to legitimize preeminence under the pretext that China is assumed reactionary and seeks hegemonic stance. CDA thus exhibits how linguistic choices and map strategic mobilization to naturalize competing geopolitical truths as intellectuals and scholars engage with organized, rational, malleable "truths."

2.3. Media Framing, Intertextuality and Historical Memory

Media organizations promote narratives of danger and power in social reality by the way of framing and intertextual reference. Tahira and Mir (2025) have provided an example of how news outlets from both the U.S. and China have utilized Cold War metaphors and the memory of historical Cold War events namely "containment," "hegemony," and "peaceful rise" to substantiate the ideological underpinning of their nation's foreign policy behaviour. Sehar and Anwar (2025) have discovered that peace frames and narratives have been pushed to the margins in favour of frames and narratives that emphasize polarization which increases the appearance of dominance as a defence mechanism against aggression. Similarly, Mohammad and Abid (2021) have discovered that referring to the earlier global crises as a form of intertextuality also supports a framed and mediated fear of China. Lu (2023) argues that the U.S. and China both deploy historical tropes to buttress ideological competition: the U.S. is the protector of democracy while China is the challenger of the longstanding Western hierarchy. Butt, Anwar, and Anwar (2025) have indicated in their media mood analysis that the grammatical mood (imperative or declarative) used by textual authors amplifies ideological positioning and moral judgment both of which are highly common in Western reporting of China's assertiveness. Repeating and employing intertextual echo in media discourse helps to normalize rivalry as a stable, accepted possible outcome. These studies show how news organizations and spokespeople for the nation both share semiotic codes the metaphors of competition, race and containment even across disparate geopolitical contexts. There is a discursive continuity to these semiotic codes with earlier context of the Cold War rhetoric. Therefore, intertextuality serves two purposes: it is memory and weapon at the same time, allowing the narratives of power to

seem historically justified while it simultaneously limits the spacial comfort for cooperation.

2. 4. Research Gap

Despite much critical analysis, very few comparative studies have examined either official U.S. or Chinese statements against a corpus and different methods of triangulation. Most studies have examined media reports rather than diplomatic or ministerial speech. Hu and Li (2025) have examined U.S. trade documents but did not include China's lexical counter-strategies; Xu and Xu (2025) have employed a corpus of CDA in their examination of Reuters' coverage, for example, only revealing imbalance in applying blame rather than self-representation of government. In addition, previous studies rarely assess the frequency of adversarial vocabulary versus cooperative vocabulary which would be an important indicator of rhetorical escalation. One neglected aspect even is historical intertextuality how both states invoke language from Cold War lexicons of containment and deterrence as a means of legitimizing modern competition. Lu (2023, p.2) alludes to this evolution but does not systematically comparing. Additionally, a combination of CDA would help reveal how each side re-lexicalizes history for their strategic ends. This study will contribute to these gaps by analyzing the lexical fields and discursive strategies between official U.S. and Chinese texts (2020-2025), with interpreting the findings qualitatively using CDA. It will disclose the function of ideological markers producing a richer reinterpretation of how those markers are linguistically framed and upheld to continue the asymmetrical power between the two states. Focusing on methodological and contextual issues, it contributes to critical scholarly research on global discourse, supporting the proposition that new discourse globally related to competition between the U.S. and China is not simply political rivalry but a discursive power struggle over epistemic authority.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

A qualitative research design utilizing Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) was employed to analyze how officials in the United States and China construct narratives related to power and threat through electronic media. CDA was selected as it focuses on the connections among language, ideology and power in socio-political context (Fairclough, 1995; Van Dijk, 2008). The study is grounded in Fairclough's three-dimensional framework i.e. textual

analysis, discursive practice and social practice which facilitates a rigorous analysis of linguistic choices tied to wider ideological frameworks. The design emphasizes interpretation as a methodological approach rather than one that focuses on statistical analysis while providing a further exploration of how discourse serves as a tool of domination, legitimation and resistance in the international communicative context.

3.2 Data Collection

Data has been collected by selecting official texts and retellings from media sources in two countries in order to examine discourse-level and lexical-level patterns between the two nation-states. The study was aimed to uncover how both countries either maintain or dismantle Cold War ideologies in electronic communication environments. Data has been gathered from government electronic sources in two countries (the U.S. and China) that are publicly available for consumption by citizens of each nation. For the U.S., data sources included press briefings, official statements and interviews from the White House, the U.S. Department of State and major media sources like CNN and The Washington Post. For China, data sources included information from the Chinese Ministry of Foreign Affairs, CGTN and the Xinhua News Agency as they represent China's national interests. Newspaper articles were accessed from 2020 to 2024, representing a time that sees increased levels of geopolitical tensions and competition in rhetoric. Twenty texts were selected by purposive sampling to operate as the key texts for the study (ten from the U.S. and ten from China). The languages used in each sample and their corresponding media representations were selected based on their construction of U.S.-China relations, cold war framing and narratives of power. Texts were sourced from credible online sources to facilitate verifying accuracy and credibility. The texts were chosen based on purposive sampling, appropriate for qualitative research involving texts chosen due to their discursive richness and ideological implications (Bryman, 2016). Only official governmental responses or media statements, directly quoted in the respective news articles, were included to only cover governmental discursive practices as opposed to media commentary.

The data has been analyzed based on three-dimension CDA as outlined by Fairclough (1995):

- **Textual Dimension** - Analysis of vocabulary, modality and lexical repetition in analyzing ideological patterns.

- **Discursive Dimension** - Analysis of how the texts came to be through production and dissemination through electronic media.
- **Social Dimension** - An analysis situating discursive patterns in broader social context, including geopolitical and ideological conditions specific to US-China relations.

During the textual dimension of analysis, the research has coded vocabulary, including "threat," "cooperation," "aggression," "sovereignty," and "cold war" to develop any repeating patterns of representation. It has also developed discursive strategies, including othering; legitimization; moral polarization and victimization. Findings were presented through the ideological square (Van Dijk, 1998), to interpret in what ways the groups were emphasizing their positive self-presentation and the negative presentation of others. Interpretation was aimed at exploring how the lexical items dispensed by both groups, continued to linguistic reproduction of global hierarchies of power and threat perception.

3.3 Data Analysis

Theme 1: Lexical Choices in Constructing the Cold War Narratives

Lexical choice operates as an impactful discursive mechanism through which both the United States and China construct, sustain and contest Cold War narratives in new media. Fairclough (2015) notes that vocabulary choices reveal ideological positioning and the representatives of the United States continually use the terms, "competition," "security," "aggression," "values," and "democracy." Such words all indicate the U.S. position as defender of the global order and democratic principles. The statements, "China threatens the rules based international system," and "we are going to defend freedom in the Indo-Pacific," suggest a moral imperative. Repeated use of these terms in U.S. outlets, like CNN and The Washington Post, reinforces perceptions of China as an existential systems threat. Framing, like these Cold War-era phrases, takes America's role as defender against authoritarian expansionism and presents it as the interests of the good of moral duty. This lexical choice within American discourse functions for ideological effects that transform the discourse's interpretation of geopolitical rivalry into moral imperative. The representation of the U.S. as a stabilizing military power rests largely on terminology that invokes virtuousness and claims global stewardship, thereby obfuscating its strategic ambitions through a linguistic frame of morality. Alternatively, Chinese regime representatives adopt a distinctly different lexical frame

which emphasizes collaboration, peaceful development, sovereignty, mutual respect and non-interference. Recurring tropes like “Cold War mentality” function as a linguistic weapon against U.S. ideological framing positions indexed to discourse. By connecting/characterizing U.S. behavior to the narrative of “the Cold War,” China can position itself as progressive and dedicated to peace.

Lexical strategy not only dismisses binary cognitive patterns inherited from past ideological conflicts but it also repositions China’s ascent as legitimate and peaceful. For example, statements by the Chinese Foreign Ministry emphasize that “China will continue to follow a path of peaceful development and oppose bloc confrontation (Li et al., 2023; Iqbal & Hussain., 2017).” These lexical efforts frame China as a rational participant in global order rather than as potentially aggressive. Chinese electronic media outlets, like CGTN and Xinhua, have relied on these terms in their own framing efforts, reinforcing a discourse of responsible leadership in contrast to American provocation. By doing so, Chinese officials have constructed a moral identity connected to harmony, cooperation and respect for sovereignty which subverted U.S. representations of threat. The differences in the American and Chinese lexical fields indicate a deep ideological polarization that reflects the possibility of larger struggles for power. The United States uses vocabulary with connotations as “defense,” “freedom,” and “responsibility,” while China’s field of terms includes “dialogue,” “respect,” and “mutual benefit.” The lexical distance ultimately constructs two competing realities of the same global context. The U.S. discourse draws from a sense of moral authority and reinforces Van Dijk’s (1998) ideological square; the United States generates a positive self-image, while other states become the negative representations in response. In addition, China’s discourse reverses the ideological square by creating a hegemonic representation of the U.S., while presenting itself as a virtuous alternative to U.S. foreign policy. These narratives create an us-versus-them perspective and electronic media maintains this narrative by continually and selectively repeating official terminology, only reinforcing ideological divisions for a global media audience. In the end, lexical choice becomes not just a linguistic choice but a symbolic act of identity construction. In speaking about self and other, both states turn diplomatic differences into moral battles.

The persistence of these lexical assets over time and via different platforms demonstrates an intentional effort to perpetuate discursive dominance in IR. Intertextuality also indicates that the choice of lexicon by both sides draws upon the historical resonances of the first Cold War. U.S. officials equivocate and say, "This isn't a new Cold War, but is a competition of systems" which both repudiates and resurrects Cold War imagery. This contradictory duality delivers a moral continuity to the U.S. as a worthy historical protector of global order. Chinese officials deny the Cold War imagery through lexical negation, asserting that "the world doesn't need another Cold War." In some sense, this rejection constructs a moral binary: China is peace and process while the U.S. is regression. These intertextual reverberations are particularly important because they ground emotional and historical weight in contemporary diplomacy. Fairclough (1995) advances that these linguistic resonances link micro-level lexical choices to macro-reproduction of ideologies. Therefore, by virtue of their lexical choices, both the U.S. and Chinese states reconstitute a Cold War framing for the digital world. The U.S. lexicon justifies containment as protection whereas the China'd lexicon justifies resistance as self-defense. Lexical choices, then, are not only communicative signs, they also are ideological templates for how global audiences will construct understandings of legitimacy, threat and cooperation.

Theme 2: Discursive Strategies of Threat and Power Construction

In addition to lexical patterns, U.S. and Chinese officials employ distinct discursive strategies to construct narratives of threat and power. Using Fairclough's (2001) concept of discourse as social practice, these strategies reveal how power operates through language. The U.S. discourse utilizes strategies of othering, legitimation and moral polarization. Through phrases like "China's coercive economic practices" and "military assertiveness," U.S. officials represent China as a destabilizing actor. This narrative also creates a moral binary of democracy versus authoritarianism. The U.S. self-representation as the protector of a "rules-based order" serves to legitimate its containment policies as acts of moral obligation rather than as acts of power. Van Dijk's (2008) ideological square, in which "our good" and "their bad" is emphasized, is at play here, whereby American discourse produces a moral elevated self-representation while characterizing China as the offender of international norms. These strategies perform a rhetorical action that converts power projection into moral obligation and makes

"acting dominant" into moral "defense" against a "bad actor." To counter the ideological framing, Chinese officials employ strategies of reversal, delegitimization and victimization. The term hegemonism commonly appears in Chinese statements which describes the U.S. positionality in a coercive and self-serving manner. In Sumida's examples, Chinese officials use the charge of "bullying," "interference," and "containment" repeatedly to shape discourse in which they reposition themselves as victims of aggression experiencing instability rather than as the ones causing it. By reversing discourse in this way, a defensive sovereignty is constructed whereby China's actions, such as evidence of military modernization or in asserting its economic expansion is justified as defensive posturing responding to some provocation to its sovereignty. Additionally, China's invocation of "win-win cooperation" and "mutual respect" operates as a legitimating discourse that appeals to the developing world and seeks to present itself as an alternative to Western dominance.

Through the electronic media like CGTN, as well as the Global Times, these mechanisms of self-representation are amplified and recast China as a force for fairness and balance. As a means of strategizing, it is important to remember, Chinese officials have shifted the threat from China to the United States and have changed the global characterizations of legitimacy and power. A detailed investigation of modality and intertextuality demonstrates how both countries invoke legitimacy with their language. For example, U.S. officials utilize high modality expressions "must protect," "will defend," "should ensure" which linguistically expresses certainty and dominance. Fairclough (2015) uses modality as a feature used by an institution due to its' duty and control. Chinese officials, in contrast, employ collective and mitigated modality; for example, "should jointly," "need to," or "seek common ground," all of which subtly project a sense of inclusiveness and decrease aggressiveness and tension, while still asserting China's position as equal. Repetition of collective pronouns such as "we" and "our partners" further the projection of multilateralism. Thus, modality constitutes an ideological act in both U.S. bias expressions of dominance with obligations and in Chinese bias expressions of legitimacy with cooperation. Both forms mentioned above demonstrate how linguistic expression can invoke geopolitical reasoning and ideological persuasion and the discourse of electronic media plays an important role as a mechanism for increasing observed discursive strategies. For example, examples of

linguistic expression consistent with U.S. government references of "security," "competition," and "freedom" on western media outlets (CNN, BBC) serves to reinforce a global discourse of United States moral leadership. Chinese media, like CGTN and People's Daily, rethinks the same events with discourses of "provocation," "double standards," and "unilateralism."

This media recontextualization turns official government rhetoric into public ideology. As Fairclough (1995) states, media serves as means of ideological reproduction, constructing the ways society is to conceive conflict and cooperation. The U.S. authorizes a capital city as part of the means of supporting its hegemonic identity through recontextualization within media visibility. China recontextualizes its capital city in a way that promotes a different world order based on sovereignty and respect. The various discursive strategies developed by both countries exhibit power not solely as military or economic capacity but rely on discursive control (the potential to determine or shape reality and legitimize behavior) by using language. In short, CDA draws attention to how the labeling of threat and power in electronic media occurs through language while serving a geopolitical purpose to reveal that discourse also becomes an arena for global competition.

4. CONCLUSION

The investigation of U.S. and Chinese officials' discourse from electronic media outlets (2020-2025) reveals two related but differently constructed narratives. The U.S. discourse depicts China as a systemic threat to the liberal international order, with lexicon like "aggression," "unfair," "authoritarian," and "security risk" serving to mark moral superiority and justify containment. Through othering and moral polarization discursive techniques, U.S. officials position themselves as defenders of global democracy and characterize competition as defensive rather than expansive. Intertextually, the original Cold War resonates through phrases like "strategic deterrence" and "freedom vs. coercion." Conversely, the Chinese discourse exemplifies the legitimacy and victimization strategies with China being characterized as a peaceful actor of provoked and mischaracterized responses to Western hegemony. Lexical clusters like "win-win cooperation," "mutual respect," and "non-interference" signal a counter-narrative aiming to restore moral and ideological legitimacy. Because the U.S. creates rhetoric signaling external threat, China's narrative emphasizes internal harmony and global partnership while indirectly making the case for soft power

dominance. Both narratives signal discursive mirroring with each protagonist seeking to justify their identities while projecting aggression to the other. The lexical difference is tone and moral framing; the U.S. foregrounds threat to justify its influence while China foregrounds peace to normalize its power. This structure maintains a linguistic Cold War where dominance over a narrative becomes its own source of power. Ultimately, we conclude that U.S.-China Cold War narratives are more than geopolitical phenomena but rhetorical constructions shaped through angles of lexical choices and rhetorical strategies.

By employing Critical Discourse Analysis, this study illustrates that both the United States and China invoke linguistic properties to encode ideological intentions: the U.S. through threat rhetoric that normalizes authority and China through cooperative rhetoric that protects sovereignty. This dual framing maintains a perpetuating discourse that is ethnocentric-suspiciousness combined with moral self-legitimation and order. These outcomes support Fairclough's (1995) position in which discourse in itself is both a product and a producer of social power. Both powers repeatedly invoked historical metaphors, moral binaries, and political othering, which the study argues was a performance of dominance within the realm of discourse or communicative action before it becomes a dominant order in policy. The legitimacy of the discursive strategies (the theoretical constructs) that the present study has identified while mostly concerning othering, legitimization and intertextual memory show that modern Cold War rhetoric persists not in obvious hostilities but to normalize the competition through language. The findings illustrate how lexical asymmetry is reflective of the ideological asymmetry of the positions and that when the media increases the salience of these elite understandings of reality, they transform into public belief systems. There is an opportunity for future research to take this lens to the regional media or digital diplomacy to explore how the narratives of power change as they cross linguistic and cultural boundaries. Finally, the study suggests that the "new Cold War," at least in discursive form is a war of words as much as it is of policies where the authority for dominance continues to be perpetuated through undiscursive language of legitimacy, threat and moral claim.

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